

***Evidence-Based Toxicology* Guide to Manuscript Handling Process**

Evidence-Based Toxicology is committed to a very high degree of transparency in its processes for manuscript submission and evaluation. Through these processes, we also aim to generate useful information about published research, ensure accountability of the journal for the decisions that it makes, and allow all involved parties to be credited for their contribution to the manuscript evaluation process. By doing this, we believe we are able to significantly increase the value of triage and peer-review for authors, reviewers, and users of research.

Our commitment to transparency and community value means we have an almost unique process for handling submissions. It consists of three main components: the submission of the manuscript as a registered preprint; the process of open assessment of the manuscript; and the summarisation in each journal issue of the current status of each manuscript that we have received.

EBT has two submission pathways for manuscripts: direct submissions, and submissions via the Peer Community in Registered Reports (PCI-RR). PCI-RR submissions should follow the relevant community guidance for Level 1 submissions. Submissions via the direct route will be handled according to the processes below. Detailed instructions for authors of PCI-RR submissions [can be found here](#).

Manuscript submission

All submitted manuscripts are treated as “Working Papers”, meaning they are summaries of planned or completed research projects for which the documentation is still in active development.

Authors submit a Working Paper by registering it on the [EBT Community of the Zenodo.org preprint repository](#). This includes the supplemental materials and reporting checklists that are required for the given submission type.

Authors then send a cover letter to the journal via the [submission system](#) stating that they wish to have their Working Paper considered for publication.

Submitted Working Papers enter our Assessment Process, where editors, peer-reviewers, and authors collaborate to determine whether the Working Paper is a sufficient unit of contribution to evidence-based toxicology that it can be considered an Accepted addition to the literature.

Assessment

The assessment process consists of two stages: editorial triage, and peer-review.

Editorial triage

All submitted Working Papers are triaged by a Handling Editor. In this process, the Handling Editor completes the relevant Triage Questionnaire for the submission type, to come to a judgement about whether the Working Paper is sufficiently developed to be advanced to peer review.

Triage is primarily intended as a check on compliance with relevant methodological standards, screening for issues that critically affect the utility, transparency, and/or credibility of the study. This is to ensure that limited peer-review resources are not spent on Working Papers that still need fundamental work.

The Handling Editor's judgement and reasoning are summarised in an Assessment Report. Once completed, the Assessment Report is registered on Zenodo.org and linked to the Working Paper. The DOI for the Triage Report is shared with the authors.

When triaging a Working Paper, the Handling Editor has three options:

1. Advance the Working Paper to peer-review;
2. Request revisions, then reconsider advancing the Working Paper for peer-review;
3. Decline to advance the Working Paper to peer-review.

The Handling Editor will discuss with the authors selection of option (2) or (3). (2) is the preferred option; (3) will only be chosen if the work required cannot be completed in a timeframe of approximately 2-3 months. In the event of choosing (3), authors will still be encouraged to resubmit their manuscript if they eventually address the Editor's comments.

For Working Papers that are revised in response to triage comments, the Handling Editor will evaluate the authors' responses to the issues raised and again decide from the three options

above. The Handling Editor will update the Assessment Report with further comments, and the link to the Assessment Report will be shared with the authors.

Working Papers that the Handling Editor declines to advance to peer-review are withdrawn from the Journal, with a final version of the Assessment Report uploaded to the relevant record on Zenodo.

Peer-review

Working Papers that have cleared triage will be assigned by the Handling Editor the number of peer-reviewers as specified by journal policy, unless exceptional circumstances apply.

Peer-reviewers are sent a link to the current versions of the Working Paper and Assessment Report. They are asked to identify limitations in the Paper that could potentially impact the validity or reproducibility of its findings, and describe whether the limitations should be (a) addressed through further experimental work and/or data analysis, or (b) explicitly acknowledged in the manuscript and their potential impact analysed.

Peer-reviewers are strongly encouraged to sign their comments but do have the option of remaining anonymous. Peer-reviewers who sign their comments will be listed as co-authors of the Assessment Report and be eligible to be co-authors of the regular Status Editorials (see below) to which their reviewer comments relate.

Authors have three options for responding to reviewer comments:

1. Conduct further analysis or experimental work to address the limitations, or rebut the comments;
2. Acknowledge in their manuscript the limitations and describe their potential impact;
3. Withdraw their manuscript from consideration for publication.

The most appropriate response to comments will be agreed between the authors, editors, and peer-reviewers. (1) is the preferred option; (2) is preferred if the additional analysis and experimental work is not feasible; (3) is the option of last resort, if additional work is not feasible and the limitations are sufficiently critical that the study cannot reasonably be viewed as a unit of contribution to the literature. For options (1) and (2), there may be additional rounds of peer review.

Whichever option is chosen, peer-review comments are integrated into an updated Assessment Report, posted to the linked record on Zenodo.org, and the link to the Report is shared with the Authors. The Assessment Report is updated for each round of peer-review that is undertaken.

Once the editors, peer-reviewers, and authors are satisfied that a Working Paper is a sufficient unit of contribution to the field of evidence-based toxicology, it becomes an Accepted Manuscript and is formally published in the Journal.

Submission status editorials

Every two months, we publish an editorial listing the current status of each submitted manuscript that we have received. The list includes links to the preprint and any related Assessment Reports that have been created or updated. The editorial will include some qualitative and quantitative analysis of submission data and Assessment Reports as appropriate.

Because Assessment Reports are a substantial contribution to the editorial, and editors and peer-reviewers who sign their reviews are accountable for the work and its published form, editors and peer-reviewers who have contributed to Assessment Reports in the immediate period up to the previous journal issue are eligible to be named as co-authors of the Editorial.

The purpose of Submission Status Editorials is to ensure transparency of and accountability for the decisions made by the journal in relation to each submission we receive. Specifically, Submission Status Editorials aim to:

- Provide peer-reviewers and editors with formal credit for their work in assessing manuscripts
- Provide a permanent, public link between a submission and its assessment by the journal
- Make public the decisions made by the journal and the data used in making them
- Provide useful information for contextualising the findings of a study